

IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE THINKING IN MATHEMATICS

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Annotation: The article devoted to open the theme creative thinking in mathematics and its significant role modern education system. Moreover, content of Mathematical creativity and special features were noted.

Key words: *Mathematical epistemology, Heuristics, mathematical discovery, mathematical conundrums, creative insights, conceptualizing, complex mathematical theories.*

The interplay between creative thinking and mathematical problem-solving represents a fascinating domain of cognitive science and mathematics education. As we know, mathematics, a discipline often perceived as rigidly structured and rule-bound, paradoxically thrives on creative thought. This duality forms the crux of our exploration. The first dimension of this inquiry delves into epistemological foundations, where the nature of mathematical knowledge and its genesis through creative processes are dissected. Mathematical epistemology, far from being merely a collection of axiomatic truths, is deeply rooted in creative exploration and abstraction. In the realm of problem-solving, the role of heuristic algorithms emerges as pivotal. Heuristics, often derived from creative insights, guide problem solvers through uncharted territories of complex mathematical landscapes. The intricate dance between systematic methods and creative leaps is not just fascinating but essential in breaking new ground in mathematical discovery.

Cognitive schemata and their evolution play a significant role in how

mathematicians perceive and tackle problems. A schema is not a static cognitive structure; it evolves, adapts, and is often reconstructed, much like a living organism. This adaptability is often fueled by creative insights, leading to novel approaches in solving longstanding mathematical conundrums. The process of abstract reasoning, a cornerstone of mathematical thought, is deeply influenced by creative thinking. Abstract reasoning transcends concrete data, drawing upon patterns, structures, and relationships that exist in the mind's eye. This mental visualization, a form of creative thinking, is essential in conceptualizing complex mathematical theories. Another facet of this symbiosis is the concept of conceptual synthesis, where disparate ideas and theories converge through creative thought processes. This synthesis is not merely additive; it's transformative, leading to new mathematical constructs that were previously inconceivable[1].

Mathematical creativity, often shrouded in enigma, emerges as the cornerstone of groundbreaking advancements in the realm of numbers and logic. This transformative force within mathematics defies conventional boundaries, propelling the discipline beyond mere calculation into the realm of innovation and discovery. The interplay of creativity with mathematical rigor fosters a unique environment where the unforeseen becomes conceivable, and the abstract materializes into tangible solutions. At the heart of this creative paradigm is the concept of conceptual blending, a cognitive process where ideas from disparate domains coalesce to form novel mathematical concepts. This blending is not a mere amalgamation of existing notions but an alchemical process that gives birth to revolutionary ideas, reshaping the mathematical landscape. The capacity to perceive connections between seemingly unrelated concepts exemplifies the essence of mathematical creativity

Critical and creative thinking need to be embedded in every mathematics lesson[2]. When we embed critical and creative thinking, we transform learning

from disjointed, memorisation of facts, to sense-making mathematics. Learning becomes more meaningful and purposeful for students. There are many tools and many methods of promoting thinking. Using a range of problem solving activities is a good place to start, but you might want to also use some shorter activities and some extended activities. Open-ended tasks are easy to implement, allow all learners the opportunity to achieve success, and allow for critical thinking and creativity. Tools such as Bloom's Taxonomy and Thinkers Keys are also very worthwhile tasks. For good mathematical problems go to the nrich website. For more extended mathematical investigations and a wonderful array of rich tasks, my favourite resource is Maths300 (this is subscription based, but well worth the money). All of the above activities can be used in class and/or for homework, as lesson starters or within the body of a lesson. Critical and creative thinking is something we cannot ignore if we want our students to be prepared for a workforce and world that is constantly changing. Not only does it equip them for the future, it promotes higher levels of student engagement, and makes mathematics more relevant and meaningful.

Many researchers assume that people are creative, but their degree of creativity is different. The notion of creative thinking level has been discussed by experts. The perspective of mathematics creative thinking refers to a combination of logical and divergent thinking which is based on intuition but has a conscious aim. The divergent thinking is focused on flexibility, fluency, and novelty in mathematical problem solving and problem posing. As students have various backgrounds and different abilities, they possess different potential in thinking patterns, imagination, fantasy and performance; therefore, students have different levels of creative thinking[3].

Understanding the level of creative thinking among university mathematics students is important for problem-solving and innovation. Findings can inform teaching methods and curricula to promote creative thinking. Exploring the

relationship between creative thinking and variables like gender and academic achievement provides valuable insights. Developing creative thinking skills among university students is beneficial for their academic and professional pursuits. For years creativity was discouraged in schools. Teachers imposed strict guidelines for kids' assignments and there was only one correct answer and one accurate process. In that old-fashioned setup, following rules and standards was the best way to become a successful student[4]. Luckily, things started to change. Teachers slowly begun to recognize the huge importance of fostering creative thinking in the classroom. Surprisingly, math teachers are one of the pioneers of creativity-inspired teaching. Lack of creative thinking in a math classroom results in simple memorizing techniques without imagining how, where, or why to use them in real life. Setting up an environment in which mistakes are allowed, and making sure that your students know there is more than one solution to a problem will foster creativity. Math is as much about posing problems as problem-solving, and at that point, the creativity is in noticing there is something to investigate. Another powerful tool in supporting students as independent, creative thinkers is the use of questioning. In this environment, a classroom needs to value differences and learn from that diversity and creativity.

In conclusion it should be highlighted that one of the most crucial abilities in the face of global issues is creativity. Because of this, research on creativity is always intriguing, especially in the context of mathematics education. The world we have known is changing rapidly. The set of skills we have now might not be useful in few years. The ability to adapt to new conditions and situations is a crucial skill. But employers want you to look beyond the answers. Creativity is now valued as the most important business skill, and creative thinking is one of the keys to economic prosperity in the 21st century. So, how can we prepare our children for this fast-changing, hectic environment? By allowing students to nourish their creative thinking in the classroom you prepare them for the world

outside of it. Turn your classroom into an open space of free thinkers and wonderers. Allow your students to use new thinking tools, tweak solution paths, and facilitate new processes. The best way for students to learn how to think creatively is to let them think creatively. Let them test, revise, and draw conclusions from their own judgments. With time, they will become more and more confident in their thinking.

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